

SMART FISHWAYS

W3 – Development of a low-cost fish counter and environmental variable logger

D3.2 Environmental variable logger technical report and user guide

Abstract

The deliverable titled "Environmental Variable Logger Technical Report and User Guide" provides a comprehensive description of the developed environmental variable node, along with a user guide. This resource aims to facilitate the expansion of environmental variables recorded at each study case of Smart Fishways, thereby enhancing the monitoring and analysis capabilities of the system.

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Project information

Project information	
<i>Project number</i>	101032024
<i>Project acronym</i>	Smart Fishways
<i>Project title</i>	Adapting fishways to hydrological and climatic uncertainty
<i>Starting date</i>	01/09/2021
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<i>Abstract</i>	<p>Modern society currently requires large volumes of fresh water. The result is the installation of river barriers, causing the fragmentation of habitats as well as changes in the ecology of freshwater systems. Stepped fishways can allow fish to move freely up rivers to complete their life cycle. However, the variability of rivers modifies the hydraulic conditions within fishways, affecting the free movement of fish.</p> <p>Smart Fishways is an EU-funded project, which aims to assess the effect of hydrological variability on stepped fishways and to develop a technological and methodological framework to monitor fishways' performance in real-time. By combining fish biology, hydraulics and sensor networks, a new generation of smart fishways will be created, capable of self-deciding their optimal configuration.</p>
<i>Work Package number</i>	W3 Development of a low-cost fish counter and environmental variable logger
<i>Deliverable</i>	D3.2 Environmental variable logger technical report and user guide

Document Control Page

Document control Page	
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1. Introduction

The WP3 of the Smart Fishways project was focused on making the framework independent from third-party technologies. The primary goals were to reduce costs, integrate the system within a unified communication network, and enable feasible installations in any fishway. This document outlines the new design and operational guidelines for the environmental variable node/logger. The document presents the latest version of nodes, designed to integrate water level measuring sensors and environmental variables logger into a single unit. This integration incorporates the accumulated knowledge and considers previous user experiences with water level sensors (D.1.1).

The current version of the node is more cost-effective, robust, and user-friendly than its predecessors.

2. Environmental variables: Why measure environmental variables?

The ecological integrity and functionality of a fishway extend beyond its hydraulic attributes, with various environmental variables playing pivotal roles in its efficiency. For instance, water temperature is crucial as fish species thrive within specific temperature ranges that support optimal health and migration. It influences metabolic rates, spawning cues, and overall fish behavior. Monitoring water temperature is vital for assessing the fishway's suitability for different species throughout the year.

Light conditions are equally significant. They affect the diurnal and seasonal behavior of fish, with certain species exhibiting heightened activity under specific lighting. Furthermore, light penetration can influence water temperature and plant growth within the fishway. Measuring light conditions is instrumental in deciphering and forecasting fish behavior and movement patterns.

By monitoring these and other environmental variables, we can acquire a comprehensive understanding of the fishway's ecological conditions. This holistic approach is key to pinpointing potential issues, maintaining optimal conditions for aquatic life, and boosting the overall efficacy of fishway operations. Regular monitoring furnishes crucial data for adaptive management, ensuring the fishway's sustained functionality and its contribution to the ecosystem.

Moreover, by integrating the monitoring of these variables, we can evaluate the real impact of hydraulics on fishways, paving the way for the development of robust predictive models. This, in turn, aids in devising rules for management optimization, acknowledging that while we can modify hydraulic variables, other environmental variables such as temperature usually will be difficult to modify.

To facilitate the monitoring of environmental variables, we have developed a new node compatible with various analog and digital sensors. This node is powered by a custom-made microcontroller board, the Sentinel Board. This innovation not only enhances user experience but also significantly reduces the development costs of our designs, making it a strategic advancement in the field of fishway management.

3. The environmental variable node

Certain environmental factors have been shown to be intrinsically linked with fish migration, often serving as catalysts for these movements. Predominantly, fish rely on environmental cues such as light (including photoperiod and lunar cycles), water temperature, hydrological conditions (such as river discharge and water depth), meteorological factors (including rainfall and barometric pressure), and various chemical indicators (like salinity and overall water quality). These factors act as ecological signals, aligning behavioral responses such as migration, feeding, and spawning [1,2].

In response to this, it is imperative to develop a versatile monitoring node capable of integrating multiple analog and digital sensors to accurately measure these variables. Furthermore, it is crucial that these nodes or loggers allow users to configure and retrieve data efficiently and securely, especially considering their field deployment in proximity to water—a challenging environment for electronic devices.

Given these requirements, the design of such a monitoring system must adhere to the following specifications:

- **Sensor Compatibility:** The system should accommodate a diverse array of sensors, ensuring versatility in measuring various environmental parameters.
- **Wireless Data Transmission:** The node must be capable of transmitting data wirelessly to a central gateway, facilitating remote data collection and analysis.
- **Sustainable Power Source:** To ensure longevity and reliability in the field, the system should be powered by solar energy or possess a durable battery, minimizing the need for frequent maintenance.
- **Autonomous Operation:** The device should be capable of functioning autonomously in sync with other sensors, ensuring continuous and reliable data collection.
- **Cost-Effectiveness:** The technology should be affordable, with the total cost for materials and assembly not exceeding 130€, making it accessible for widespread implementation.
- **User-Friendly Design:** Operation of the device should be straightforward, preferably enabling wireless, cable-free configuration to enhance ease of use and field adaptability.

With these foundational specifications in mind, the subsequent sections will detail the architectural framework and operational design of the sensor system, paving the way for effective environmental monitoring and data-driven decision-making in aquatic ecosystem management.

3.1. Node hardware

To implement the node we developed a new microcontroller board, the MC Sentinel V1.1, a microcontroller board designed by the University of Valladolid for rapid IoT prototyping. This board integrates, in a compact form factor, an ESP32 microcontroller, an RTC (DS3231M), an SD card holder (to storage the data), and an Autopower Circuit (<https://github.com/MyCircuitsTV/Sentinel>) (Figure 1).

MC Sentinel v1.1

by My Circuits 2023

MC Sentinel board Pinout

www.mycircuits.xyz
youtube.com/@mycircuits

Figure 1. The sentinel board.

Additionally, the node incorporates a custom PCB that includes a LoRa radio module and a 18650 lithium battery holder, ensuring a battery life of at least one year with a 15-minute transmission interval. It also features easy-plugging contacts, facilitating swift sensor attachment. While the developed node is versatile, capable of accommodating a range of sensors and interfaces (I2C, Analog, SPI), the standard MC Multi setup includes an AHT20 sensor (for humidity and temperature), a BMP280 sensor (for pressure and temperature), a TSL2561 sensor (for luminosity), a DS18B20 sensor (for water temperature), and a JSN-SR04T ultrasonic sensor. All these components are connected or soldered onto a printed circuit board, which is then securely enclosed in a watertight (IP68) acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) housing (Figure 2), ensuring durability and protection against environmental elements.

Figure 2. Render of the designed PCB board and new housing.

The node is designed to not only store data independently but also to transmit it via radio. Within the sensor network, an asynchronous communication protocol has now been implemented, allowing the node to operate autonomously and making easier the sensor network configuration. Once configured, the node saves data on an SD card and transmits it to the gateway through radio communication. The gateway, equipped with an Atmel ATSAMD21G18 microcontroller board and an integrated LoRa RFM95 radio module, collects and stores the data. Subsequently, the master device, a Raspberry Pi 4, periodically retrieves this data from the connected microcontroller, processes it, and transmits it to an online server. Figure 3 illustrates the new portable gateways that utilize this asynchronous communication method, showcasing the advanced and efficient design of the system.

Figure 3. New portable gateway.

3.1.1. Detailed specifications

Table 1. Default sensor specifications. The device is compatible with different sensors and ranges.

Ultrasound	
Sensor type	JSN-SR04T
Range	250 a 4500 mm
Accuracy	±10 mm
Resolution	2 mm
Luminosity	
Sensor type	TSL2561
Range	0.1 lux up to 40,000 lux
Accuracy	2-5%
Resolution	1 lux
Humidity and temperature	
Sensor type	AHT20
Range	0% to 100% RH (Relative Humidity) / -40°C to +85°C

Accuracy	±2% RH / ±0.5°C
Resolution	0.024% RH / 0.01°C
Pressure and Temperature	
Sensor type	BMP280
Range	300 hPa to 1100 hPa / -40°C to +85°C
Accuracy	±0.12 hPa / ±1.0°C
Resolution	0.16 Pa / 0.01°C
Water Temperature	
Sensor type	DS1820
Range	-55°C to +125°C
Accuracy	±0.5°C
Resolution	0.125°C

Table 2. Logger module specifications

Real-time clock	DS3231M Accuracy ±2ppm from 0°C to +40°C Accuracy ±3.5ppm from -40°C to +85°C
Battery	Battery type: 18650, rechargeable 3.7 Volt lithium, user-replaceable
Battery Life*	Without solar more than 1 year with 5 minute or greater logging interval under a temperature of 20°C
Memory (SD-card)	8 – 246 GB, standard SD card
Weight	Approximately 200 g in air
Dimensions	159 x 86 x 60 mm
Housing materials	ABS
Logging interval	Configurable.
Battery indication	Battery voltage is logged in the data file
Environment Rating	IP68

*Tested duration. Higher durations are expected.

Table 3. Default communication module configuration. The device is compatible with different modes of communication.

Sensor type	RFM95
Protocol*	LoRa - radio
Range	> 10 km (in optimal conditions)

3.2. Gateway hardware

The gateway consists of a small single-board computer (Raspberry Pi 4). This computer is connected to an Atmel ATSAMD21G18 microcontroller with an integrated LoRa RFM95 radio module and a 4G modem via serial connection. The computer is powered by 12V, which can be connected to a solar inverter or to an integrated 12 V power supply.

3.3. Software

The node and the microcontroller connected to the gateway are programmed in C using the Arduino integrated development environment (IDE) [3]. The single-board computer is running the Raspberry Pi operating system (OS) with scheduled Python scripts (Figure 4). The code allows encrypted communication between nodes and the gateway. Each node has its address, which allows the gateway to identify each one.

Figure 4. The general software architecture of the sensor network

The individual configuration of the node is conducted wirelessly. By using a magnet, a reed switch is activated, turning on the sensor and initiating the configuration mode. This mode is sustained by keeping the magnet in contact with the node. During this time, the node creates an internal WiFi connection, facilitating the download of data and configuration of the sensor (Figure 5).

Figure 5. WiFi server generated by the node.

For additional information, readers are directed to view the introduction video for the Sentinel board at: <https://youtu.be/hyt3jwzMJIY?si=CsjwAYV6aaAJOECs>

References

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